

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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23010 | Saltmarsh plants revegetation potential to phytoremediate metal contamination in estuarine environments

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Background & Aim: Salt marshes protect coastal areas, regulate water quality, and support biodiversity but face growing threats from pollutants like metals. Some studies have shown saltmarsh plants phytoremediation potential to absorb/remove these contaminants (da Silva et al., 2014). This study evaluates revegetation with *Juncus maritimus* within two sites of the Lima river estuary, for the removal of metals from estuarine environments. **Methods:** At the beginning of the *in situ* revegetation (October 2025) and every 3 months, samples of water, plants, sediments and rhizosediments were collected for metals analysis. In the laboratory, water samples were filtered and the filters and remaining samples were dried at room temperature, subjected to high pressure microwave acidic digestion, and analysed by, atomic absorption spectrometry. **Results:** Metal analyses are in progress. Preliminary results show the presence of Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb and Zn in sediments and Zn and Cr in the surface water of the sites being revegetated, showing the need for their removal. **Conclusions:** Results will show the feasibility of saltmarsh plants revegetation as a potential phytoremediation biotechnological solution to remove metals from estuarine environments.

Keywords: Saltmarsh, *Juncus maritimus*, sediments, metals

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References:

[1] da Silva, M. N., Mucha, A. P., Rocha, A. C., Gomes, C. R., & Almeida, C. M. R. (2014). Response of two salt marsh plants to short- and long-term contamination of sediment with cadmium. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 15(3), 722-731. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-014-1041-y>

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